

AN INSIGHT TO MODERN DAY NEOLOGISMS IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Annotation: Neologism a relatively recent or isolated term, word, or phrase that may be in common use but still in the mainstream language not accepted. Neologisms often arise due to changes in culture and technology. Tens of thousands of words appear every year. Sometimes we come up with new things and need words for them. Other times we decide that something is important and needs a name. Or we get bored with old words and update them. Generally, if a word is liked by the public, it begins to enter common usage. These words are called neologisms.

Key words and expressions: Neologisms, derived word, transferred word, new combination, new words, mass media

A neologism is a new or coined word that has come into common use. If a word is fully accepted in everyday use, it is usually picked up by dictionaries and is technically no longer a neologism. Neologisms can take many forms and can be completely new or formed from existing words. For example, “mansplain” combines the words “man” and “explanation”. However, neologisms do not necessarily have to be constructed in a language. a neologism is a new word or term that appears in everyday use. A neologism has a limited lifespan, either because the neologism is officially accepted into common language (at which point it ceases to be a neologism) or it becomes unknown due to disuse.

A neologism usually takes one of the following forms:

- A new word (e.g. over-exchangers)
- A new combination of existing words (e.g. digital detox)
- A new meaning of an existing word (e.g sick)

Language is a dynamic phenomenon that clearly reflects modern society. The English lexicon has mutated over time from various parent languages, primarily Latin, French, and Old English, which originally descended from prehistoric Proto-Indo-European languages. Although some basic words go back to the basic origins of the language and have more or less retained their importance, many new words have been added over time - the social activity of any period of history. directly opposite. Each year, about 3,000 new words in each language are called neologisms.

Importance of neologisms

Language is a dynamic phenomenon that clearly reflects modern society. The English lexicon has mutated over time from various parent languages, primarily Latin, French, and Old English, which originally descended from prehistoric Proto-Indo-European languages. Although some basic words go back to the basic origins of the language and have more or less retained their importance, many new words have been added over time - the social activity of any period of history. directly opposite. Each year, about 3,000 new words in each language are called neologisms. What do the words surprise, cold, blush, and blush have in common? They were once invented by Shakespeare and they were once neologisms. A neologism is a new word or phrase that is not regularly used by most speakers and writers.

I. Examples of neologisms:

Example 1

blutter: to make a long, rambling speech about obscurity

Blutter combines other words like blabber and stutter to create a new word with a new meaning.

Example 2

One steva: the phone is muted

This word is an attempt to have a word for the sound we all know so well.

Example 3

sarcasm: the gap between the author of the sarcastic joke and the person who does not understand it

This word combines sarcasm with cliffhanger for a new word like humor.

II. Types of neologisms

As there are a variety of ways to make new words, there are a variety of types of neologisms.

A special type of neologism, portmanteaus do exactly what they say: combine two words to form a new word that combines their meanings.

- Examples of compound words:

smoke + fog = smoke

spoon + fork = spork

breakfast + lunch = brunch

- Derived words

Derivative words are words that have been adapted into English using ancient Greek and Latin expressions.

- Here are some examples of derived words:

Latin word: villa

Meaning: villa or house

- Transferred words

Transfer words take borrowed words to a whole new level because they include words taken from another language and used in an adjusted form in English.

Herbes is derived from the French herb, which means herbs

Alligator is Spanish for el lagarto lizard

Wiener dog is a German word for wiener hot dog

Due to many linguistic and extra linguistic factors, newly created units in the language are in the process of entering and influencing English. These new units, known as neologisms, help us understand the endless evolution of the English language. In addition, neologisms facilitate the process of coping with change by creating mental bridges between the old and the modern. The vocabulary of the English language is constantly changing, as neologisms are introduced through the media in the blink of an eye. The mass media is the main source and basis for the

creation of English neologisms, acting as an intermediary, an active consumer, between the English population and the language itself.

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